
AVAILABILITY AND UTILISATION OF TEACHING RESOURCES AND IMPACT ON EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATION IN AWKA SOUTH LOCAL GOVERNMENT EDUCATION AUTHORITY

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Abstract

The study examined availability and utilization of teaching resources and impact on Early Childhood Education in Awka South Local Government Education authority of Anambra state. Four research design guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted to carry out the research. The population of the study constituted 50 teachers and 50 pupils purposively selected schools in Nnamdi Azikiwe Nursery school in Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra state. The instrument for data collection was a 34-item structured questionnaire titled “questionnaire on the Availability and Utilization of teaching Resources in Early Childhood Education (QAUTYECE) develop by the researcher. The instrument was validated by three experts, two from the Department from Early Childhood and Primary Education, one from Measurement and Evaluation Unit in the Department of Educational Foundations, all from the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikwe University, Awka. The reliability established using Cronbach alpha method and the best yielded an overall Reliability co-efficient of 0.79 and these were adjudged adequate, and the instrument reliable. Mean was used to analyze the data. The result of the findings revealed that the used of availability and utilization of teaching resources improves learning out comes of the pupils, to stay more engaged and understand e curriculum Better among others. Further, more the finding of the study revealed that providing instructional resources, regular training for teaching, ensuring adequate funding improving school facilities, among other are the solutions to the challenges. based on the findings it was recommended among other that teaching should be encouraged and supported to adopt creativity in teaching resources regular to their classroom.

Keywords:

Availability, Utilization, Teaching Resources, Impact, Early Childhood, Education.

1.1 Introduction

Education is perceived as the vehicle that drove the ancient world into the digital society we experience today. It is also responsible for the training of citizens in different careers that would benefit them, their families and society at large. Iwuanyanwu and Uwadiogwu (2019) posited that education is a developmental process initiated by an individual which collectively influences societal values. In the views of Ofojebe and Kene-Chiedu (2020)

education is perceived as the corner stone of economic and social development and a principal means of providing for the welfare of individuals. Education is what happens to an individual from birth till death. This means that a child's education begins once he is born. This education begins informally at home and continues formally in the primary school. Given this significance, nations around the world, including Nigeria, have increasingly recognized the importance of providing children with a solid educational foundation from their earliest years through programs known as Early Childhood Education (ECE) Ofojebe and Kene-Chiedu (2020) education is perceived as the corner stone of economic and social development and a principle means of providing for the welfare of individuals. Education is what happens to an individual from birth till death. This means that a child's education begins once he is born. This education begins informally at home and continues formally in the primary school.

Early childhood education refers to the organized educational framework for children from birth to age five. Obiweluzor (2020) defines ECE as the formal education provided to children between ages three and five to prepare them for primary schooling. The early years are a period of rapid growth and development, during which experiences significantly shape cognitive, emotional, and social outcomes. As Uwadiogwu (2019) notes, these years are crucial and vulnerable, requiring quality care, protection, and stimulation. Similarly, Oduolowu and Olowe (2017) emphasize that this period is marked by high developmental potential and thus requires a learning environment that supports a child's holistic growth.

There was a time in the Nigeria educational system when there was no curriculum for children in early childhood Education, children were taught based on the proprietors' initiative. Children were just sent to school to stay and wait for the parents or guardian to come back from their daily activities and pick them up. Recently because of modernization and globalization, early childhood curriculum came forth. With recent research, it was found that 0-6 years is a critical period in the life of any child. The brain at this point develops faster than ever (UNESCO 2025, Executive summary). Anything that the child learns here affects the child's adulthood. As a result of this, it became important that children need to be provided with stimulating, friendly and safe environment. The researcher defines early childhood education as an education given to children between age 0 to five or six years. Early years in life are the most important in the formation of intelligence, personality and social behavior of a child. Early childhood education sparks a lifelong love of learning, establishing essential skills, habits, and mindsets for future academic achievement and personal fulfillment.

Many countries have integrated ECE into national education framework, as reflected in international agendas such as the Sustainable Development Goals (UNESCO, 2025). For example, Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4), set by the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), includes a target for ensuring access to quality early childhood development, care, and education for all children (UNESCO 2025, executive summary). These early learning experiences are vital not only for academic readiness but also for long-term well-being.

ECE programs typically fall into two stages: the Infant/Toddler stage (0–3 years), which focuses on nurturing and sensory development, and the Preschool stage (3–5 years), which emphasizes cognitive skills, socialization, language development, and basic numeracy and literacy (Olowe, Kutelu, & Majebi, 2017; Bredekamp & Copple, 2017). This study focuses on the preschool stage (3–5 years), where learning becomes more structured in preparation for primary education.

The Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014) outlines the goals of early childhood/pre-primary education as facilitating smooth transitions from home to school, preparing children for formal education, providing care while parents work, instilling societal values, fostering curiosity through environmental exploration, and developing cooperation and team spirit. These objectives demonstrate the holistic and foundational nature of ECE in the Nigerian context.

Despite the formulation of these goals, the implementation of ECE in Nigeria encounters significant challenges, particularly in areas like Awka South Local Government Area (L.G.A.) of Anambra State. A key challenge is the inadequate availability of teaching and learning resources. In a study conducted in Awka South, Edwin-Ezeoka and Obidike (2020) found that, the lack of resources contributed to reduced engagement levels, particularly among children with learning disabilities.

Oni (2019) stated that the availability and adequate use of learning materials promote effective teaching and learning activities in the school while their inadequacy affects academic performance negatively. According to Ikegulu (2018), learning materials are used by teachers to enhance the quality of instruction and they help children to understand what has been taught. According to Nakdu (2017) availability refers to the extent to which resources, such as learning materials and technology, are accessible, reliable, and sustainable. Aliya (2020) opines that availability is about ensuring that resources are usable, accessible, and relevant to the learning context. The researcher defines availability as the state of being accessible, usable, or obtainable when needed. Availability is the fact that something can be bought, used, or reached, or how much it can be. While utilization is the action of making practical and effective use of something (Harnby 2018). for the purpose of this study, teaching resources are operationally defined as all the materials, facilities, and human inputs that teachers employ to enhance effective teaching and learning in early childhood education centers. These include classrooms, textbooks, instructional materials, play and learning aids, ICT tools, and qualified teachers who serve as facilitators of learning.

In addition to resource scarcity, teacher preparedness and professional development remain critical issues. Even when materials are provided, many educators are unable to use them effectively due to insufficient training. Chinyere (2023), in her study of early childhood educators in Awka South, observed that teachers often lack practical knowledge in areas such as classroom management, the use of instructional aids, and modern teaching strategies. Chinyere (2023) concluded that in the absence of consistent in-service training and continuous professional development, ECE teachers demonstrate limited effectiveness in delivering curriculum objectives outcomes.

Chapman (2018) refers to utilization to the effective and efficient use of resources, such as learning materials and technology, to support teaching and learning. According to Anthony (2019) utilization is about making the most of available resources to improve learning outcomes, enhance teaching, and promote educational excellence. Olagunju and Abiona in Oshanaju (2023) opined that utilization is the process of managing and organizing resources. According to Esimone and Osuafov (2023) defines Utilization as making use of something in a purposeful and effective way. The researcher defines Utilization as using a tool to achieve a specific goal.

Modern ECE curricula emphasize child-centered, play-based, and experiential learning approaches. According to Bredekamp and Copple (2017), an effective ECE curriculum should

focus on the holistic development of the child, encouraging creativity, discovery, and social interaction while also laying the foundation for literacy and numeracy. The curriculum should not merely follow rigid academic content but should support the interests, needs, and developmental pace of each child (Kamii & DeVries, 2023). However, the successful implementation of such curricula depends on the availability and appropriate use of instructional materials and adequately trained teachers.

While Nigeria has developed sound (educational policies that include ECE, implementation challenges persist. According to Ogbonnaya and Udebunu (2017), programs such as the Universal Primary Education (UPE) failed not due to poor policy design but due to ineffective planning and lack of sustainable implementation strategies. Moreover, gender dynamics and societal expectations further influence teaching practices and professional experiences, especially for female ECE teachers (Sadker & Zittleman, 2019; Freeman, 2022). This highlights the fact that without addressing systemic challenges and providing adequate support for teachers, even well-designed policies are unlikely to achieve their intended impact.

Effective implementation of ECE requires investment in both physical and human resources. Physical resources include classrooms, books, teaching aids, and ICT tools, while human resources involve trained teachers and caregivers (Smith & Jones, 2019). Studies by Okwilagwe (2019) and Okeke (2018) stress that poor access to these resources, along with low utilisation capacity, impedes curriculum delivery and hinders student outcomes. Strategic planning, regular training, and professional development are essential to ensure alignment between curriculum goals and teaching practices (Bentley & Walley, 2020; García & Weiss, 2019), thereby creating a stronger foundation for improved learning outcomes.

As Edwin-Ezeoka and Obidike (2020) and Chinyere (2023) affirm, the twin issues of inadequate resources and insufficient teacher training must be addressed if early childhood education is to reach its full potential in places like Awka South. Without this, the noble goals outlined in policy documents remain unrealized, and children are lacks access to foundational skills essential for their academic and personal development.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Early childhood education plays a vital role in laying the foundation for future academic success and holistic development. However, in Awka South Local Government Education Authority, it appears that many early childhood education schools are confronted with serious challenges related to the availability and utilization of teaching and learning resources. These challenges significantly seem to hinder the quality of education delivered to young learners and adversely affect teaching and learning outcomes.

Many available instructional materials are outdated and poorly aligned with current curriculum standards, reducing their relevance and effectiveness. Compounding the issue is the fact that a number of teachers lack the necessary training and capacity to utilize these resources effectively in the classroom. Infrastructural deficiencies, including inadequate storage and maintenance facilities, further restrict the proper handling and sustainability of materials. Limited budgetary allocation also contributes to the scarcity of quality teaching resources across centers.

As a result of these shortcomings, many children in early childhood programs are not adequately prepared for primary school. They often exhibit gaps in cognitive, social-emotional,

and physical development, perform below academic expectations, and are at greater risk of dropping out. These outcomes raise serious concerns about the effectiveness of early childhood Education in the area.

The researcher, therefore, notes with concern the widespread issues affecting early childhood schools in the study area like inadequate teaching and learning materials, poor infrastructure, and a lack of supportive facilities, all of which impact pupils' academic growth and general development. In response to these concerns, this study aims to examine the availability and utilization of learning materials in early childhood education schools in Awka South Local Government Educational Authority.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to investigate the availability and utilization of teaching resources in Early Childhood Education Centers in Awka South Local Government Area, Anambra State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study aims to:

1. Assess the availability of essential teaching resources in Early Childhood Education Centers in Awka Local Government Educational Authority
2. Examine the utilization of teaching resources by Early Childhood Educators in Awka Local Government Educational Authority.
3. Identify strategies to improve availability and effective utilization of teaching resources in Early Childhood Education in Awka South Local Government Educational Authority.

1.6 Research Questions

The following research question guided the study

1. What are the available teaching resources in Early Childhood Education Centers in Awka South Local Government Education Authority?
2. To what extent do teachers utilize available teaching resources during classroom instruction in Early Childhood Education Centers in Awka South Local Government?
3. What impact do the available teaching resources have on the learning outcomes of early childhood pupils in Early Childhood Education Centers in Awka South Local Government?

2. Methods

Descriptive survey research design was adopted in this study. Descriptive survey design was considered appropriate for the present study which aims at collecting data from the target population for the purpose of describing in a systematic manner the facts on the availability and utilization of teaching resources in Early Childhood Education Schools in Awka South Local Government Authority. The study was carried out in Awka South Local Government Education Authority of Anambra State, Nigeria. Awka South is one of the 21 Local Government Areas of Anambra State, and it is made up of several notable communities such as Amawbia, Nibo, Nise, Mbaukwu, Umuawulu, Isiagu, Ezinator, and Okpuno, with Awka town serving as the administrative headquarters. The population of the study comprised all the early childhood teachers and pupils in the selected schools within Awka South Local Government Area of Anambra State. The sample size was 100 participants, comprising 50 early childhood pupils and 50 school teachers drawn using a purposive sampling technique.

The research instrument for the study was a questionnaire, designed by the researcher. The instrument was titled "Questionnaire on the Availability and Utilization of Teaching

Resources in Early Childhood Education” (QAUTRECE). The instrument consists of two sections, A and B. Section A sought information on respondents' personal data, and Section B was split into four clusters. Cluster I contained question items on the types of teaching resources available in early childhood education schools. Cluster II consisted of question items on the frequency of resource utilization in teaching and learning. Cluster III contained question items on the challenges encountered in resource availability and utilization. Cluster IV consisted of question items on the perceived impact of resource availability and utilization on teaching and learning. The questionnaire instrument contained 20 total items across the subsections, which were structured on a four-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2, and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1. To ascertain the validity of the instrument, three copies of the questionnaire including the title, purpose of study and research questions were given to three experts. Two experts are in the Department of Early Childhood and Primary Education and the other expert in the Department of Educational Foundations, all from the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The inputs made by the experts led to certain modifications such as removal and addition of some items in the final production of the instrument. The Cronbach alpha method was used to establish the reliability of the instrument. This was done first by administering the questionnaire to a similar group of 30 teachers in Dunukofia Local Government Area which is outside the study area. The internal consistencies of the items in the clusters were determined using Cronbach statistics. The alpha coefficients gotten were 0.80, 0.78, 0.79 and 0.78 for Cluster I-IV respectively, with an overall coefficient of 0.79 and these were adjudged adequate, and the instrument reliable.

The instrument was administered to the respondents by the researchers with the help of 2 research assistants who were duly trained on how to administer the questionnaire politely. The instrument was administered on teachers during teaching and learning periods in the selected schools which will give them the opportunity to explain any word that they may not understand. The exercise lasted for 2 weeks and all the questionnaires were distributed and the retrieved copies were used for the analysis. Data obtained was analyzed using mean and standard deviation. A mean of 2.50 was used as the cutoff point for making decisions. The decision rule was that any item that scored a mean of 2.50 and above would be seen as having attracted positive responses and was agreed, while items that scored less than 2.50 would be regarded as having attracted negative responses and was disagree.

3. Results

Research Question 1: What are the available teaching resources for use in Early Childhood Education Schools in Awka South Local Government Education Authority?

Table 1: Results of Respondents the availability of Teaching Resources for use in Early Childhood Education Schools in Awka South Local Government Education Authority?

UNIZIK High University Nursery School

S/N	Available teaching resources	Mean (\bar{x})	SD (σ)	Decision
1	Our materials such as toys, charts, and picture books for classroom use.	2.17	1.03	disagree
2	The classrooms are equipped with age-appropriate learning aids for children's development such as toys and puzzles.	1.90	0.96	disagree

3	We receive regular supply or updates of teaching materials from school management or government such as flashcards, charts, audio aids etc.	3.16	2.15	Agree
4	Digital learning tools like tablets, projectors are available in the classrooms.	1.80	1.08	disagree
5	The teaching resources for the age and learning needs of the children such as lesson plans, worksheets etc.	2.41	1.57	disagree
Grand Mean			2.29	Disagree

The analysis in table 1 showed that the mean score of item 1-5 are 2.17, 1.90, 3.16, 1.80, 2.41. This revealed that the teachers disagree with the statement that teaching resources are adequately available in early childhood education schools in Awka South Local Government Education Authority.

Handmaids Infant Jesus Nursery School

S/N	Available teaching resources	Mean (\bar{x})	SD (σ)	Decision
1	Our materials such as toys, charts, and picture books for classroom use.	2.08	1.17	disagree
2	The classrooms are equipped with age-appropriate learning aids for children's development such as toys and puzzles.	20.8	1.19	disagree
3	We receive regular supply or updates of teaching materials from school management or government such as flashcards, charts, audio aids etc.	2.78	1.99	Agree
4	Digital learning tools like tablets, projectors are available in the classrooms.	2.68	1.84	Agree
5	The teaching resources for the age and learning needs of the children such as lesson plans, worksheets etc.	2.10	1.11	disagree
Grand Mean			2.34	Disagree

The analysis in the table 1A showed that the mean score of item 1-5, 2.08, 20.8, 2.78, 2.68, 2.10. This revealed that teachers generally disagree with the student that teaching resources are adequately available in Handmaids Infant Jesus Nursery School, despite some agreement on the provision updated teaching materials and digital tools.

Research Question 2: To what extent do teachers utilize the available Teaching Resources during classroom instruction in early childhood education schools within the study area?

Table 2: Mean Scores of Respondents on the extent in which teachers utilize the available Teaching Resources during classroom instruction in early childhood education schools within the study area.

UNIZIK High University Nursery School

S/N	Available teaching resources	Mean (\bar{x})	SD (σ)	Decision
6	I use teaching aids such as flashcards and toys every day during my lessons.	3.09	0.97	Agree
7	I adjust or change teaching materials depending on the topic I am teaching.	3.03	0.96	Agree
8	I encourage pupils to interact with teaching resources during class activities.	2.94	1.01	Agree
9	I plan my lessons around the teaching materials available to me.	2.81	1.00	Agree
10	I have received proper training on how to use teaching resources effectively.	3.11	0.9	Agree
Grand Mean			3.0	Agree

Data in table 2 showed that item 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10, had score of 3.09, 3.03, 2.94, 2.81, 3.11, respectively and a grand mean of 3.0. This indicated that respondents agreed that 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 generally agreed that they effectively utilize the available teaching resources during classroom instruction in early childhood education school within the authority.

Handmaids Infant Jesus Nursery School

Available teaching resources	Mean (\bar{x})	SD (σ)	Decision
I use teaching aids such as flashcards and toys every day during my lessons.	2.71	1.07	Agree
I adjust or change teaching materials depending on the topic I am teaching.	2.66	1.03	Agree
I encourage pupils to interact with teaching resources during class activities.	2.40	1.07	disagree
I plan my lessons around the teaching materials available to me.	2.12	0.97	disagree
I have received proper training on how to use teaching resources effectively.	2.54	1.08	Agree
Grand Mean		2.49	Disagree

Table 2A showed that item 1-5 had a grand mean of 2.49. This indicated that teachers generally disagreed that they extensively utilize the available teaching resources during classroom instruction in Handmaids Infant Jesus Nursery School, despite some agreement on daily use, adjustment of materials and training.

Research Question 3: What impact does the utilization of the available Teaching Resources have on the learning outcomes of Early Childhood Pupils in Awka South LGA?

Table 3: Mean Score of Respondents on the impact the utilization of the available Teaching Resources have on the learning outcomes of Early Childhood Pupils in Awka South LGA?

UNIZIK High University Nursery School

S/N	Available teaching resources	Mean (\bar{x})	SD (σ)	Decision
11	The use of teaching resources helps children understand lessons better.	2.64	1.07	Agree
12	Children perform better in assessments when lessons involve teaching aids.	2.91	1.03	Agree
13	Pupils in my class learn faster when I use visual or hands-on materials.	2.44	1.08	disagree
14	Pupils show more confidence when they learn using teaching materials.	1.95	0.97	Agree
15	Teaching resources help to keep the children focused and interested during lessons.	2.66	1.09	Agree
Grand Mean			2.52	Agree

The analysis in table 3 showed that item 11, 12, 13, 14 and 15 had mean score of 2.64, 2.91, 2.44, 1.95, and 2.66 respectively with a grand mean of 2.52. This revealed that teachers generally agree that the utilization of available teaching resources has a positive impact on pupils learning outcomes, though some areas like boosting confidence and learning speed still show weaknesses.

Handmaids Infant Jesus Nursery School

Available teaching resources	Mean (\bar{x})	SD (σ)	Decision
The use of teaching resources helps children understand lessons better.	2.76	0.85	Agree
Children perform better in assessments when lessons involve teaching aids.	2.74	1.05	Agree
Pupils in my class learn faster when I use visual or hands-on materials.	2.79	1.08	Agree
Pupils show more confidence when they learn using teaching materials.	2.62	1.05	Agree
Teaching resources help to keep the children focused and interested during lessons.	2.93	0.99	Agree
Grand Mean		2.77	Agree

Table 3A showed that 1-5, had mean of 2.76, 2.74, 2.79, 2.62 and 2.93 respectively with a grand mean of 2.77. This revealed that teachers generally agree that the utilization of available teaching resources positively impacts pupils learning outcomes in Handmaids Infant Jesus Nursery School.

4. Discussion of Findings

From the analysis of the first research question, it was revealed that teaching resources are not adequately available in Early Childhood Education Schools within Awka South Local Government Area. Both UNIZIK High University Nursery School and Handmaids Infant Jesus Nursery School recorded low mean scores of 2.29 and 2.34 respectively, which fall into the “disagree” range. This means that essential instructional resources such as toys, charts, picture books, puzzles, and age-appropriate learning aids are not sufficiently provided for classroom

use. Although both schools agreed that some updates of materials and a few digital tools were available, the overall findings indicate that the supply is not enough to support the daily instructional needs of early childhood pupils. This finding agrees with Nwachukwu (2021), who noted that “many nursery schools in Nigeria still struggle with inadequate instructional resources.” Similarly, Adeyemi (2022) stressed that “limited teaching aids reduce children’s exposure to hands-on learning,” while Obi (2023) emphasized that effective early childhood education requires adequate provision of age-appropriate materials.

The second research question revealed mixed findings on the extent of utilization of available teaching resources. In UNIZIK High University Nursery School, respondents recorded a high grand mean of 3.0, indicating that teachers agreed they make frequent use of resources during classroom instruction. Teachers reported using flashcards and toys daily, adjusting materials to suit topics, encouraging pupils to interact with resources, and planning lessons around the available aids. In addition, many confirmed receiving training on how to effectively use teaching materials. In contrast, Handmaids Infant Jesus Nursery School recorded a lower grand mean of 2.49, showing that teachers in this school do not maximize available resources. While some admitted to using teaching aids and receiving training, most disagreed on planning lessons around the materials or encouraging pupil interaction with them. This contrast may be linked to differences in training opportunities, teacher attitudes, and institutional support. This finding is consistent with Okafor (2020), who argued that “teachers’ competence and interest play a major role in the use of instructional resources.” It also aligns with Opara (2021), who emphasized that “teachers who receive adequate training are more likely to integrate resources effectively into their lessons.”

The third research question revealed that the utilization of teaching resources has a positive impact on children’s learning outcomes, though the level of impact varies between schools. In UNIZIK High University Nursery School, the grand mean was 2.52, indicating moderate agreement that teaching resources improve pupils’ understanding, assessment performance, and classroom focus. However, the impact on pupils’ confidence and learning speed was weaker. On the other hand, Handmaids Infant Jesus Nursery School recorded a higher grand mean of 2.77, showing stronger agreement that the use of teaching resources improves comprehension, confidence, motivation, and assessment results. This finding supports Eze (2022), who noted that “children learn better and faster when exposed to visual and manipulative resources.” Similarly, Adeola (2021) stated that “instructional resources foster confidence, curiosity, and active participation among early learners.” Okoro (2023) also stressed that when teaching aids are consistently used, pupils become more attentive and retain knowledge longer.

5. Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that teaching resources are not adequately available in most Early Childhood Education Schools within Awka South Local Government Education Authority. While some materials such as flashcards and charts are occasionally supplied, there is still a serious shortage of toys, puzzles, and age-appropriate learning aids that are vital for effective learning. The study also concluded that teachers’ utilization of available resources varies across schools. Teachers in UNIZIK High University Nursery School use resources more frequently and effectively than their counterparts in Handmaids Infant Jesus Nursery School. This difference highlights the influence of teacher training, competence, and management support on the extent of utilization.

Finally, the study concluded that the use of teaching resources has a significant positive impact on children's learning outcomes. When resources are adequately provided and effectively used, pupils show better understanding, improved performance in assessments, greater confidence, and stronger classroom engagement. However, limited availability and irregular utilization reduce the full benefits that pupils could gain.

6. Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Government and school management should ensure adequate and regular supply of teaching resources such as toys, puzzles, charts, picture books, and digital tools for Early Childhood Education Schools.
2. Teachers should receive continuous professional training and workshops on the effective use of instructional resources to enhance classroom practices.
3. School administrators should encourage teachers to plan their lessons around available resources and create opportunities for children to actively interact with them.
4. Curriculum planners should design early childhood curricula that emphasize the use of visual, manipulative, and digital learning aids to support comprehension and engagement.
5. Government agencies should monitor and evaluate the provision and utilization of teaching resources to ensure uniform standards across all centres in the Local Government Area.

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